

Proximal Femur Endoprosthesis (Indications for Oncologic Pathology) Systematic Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The proximal femur is a very common location for primary malignant tumors, aggressive benign tumors, and one of the most frequent sites in the appendicular skeleton for the presentation of metastatic disease.

Thanks to advances in oncology, which have achieved better local and global control of the disease, new pathways have opened for alternatives such as limb preservation and reconstruction. There are various reconstruction alternatives, among which endoprostheses stand out. Current studies have consistently demonstrated that these implants effectively treat local disease, offer good survival rates and patient acceptance, provide reproducible functional results, and present complication rates similar to those of conventional prostheses used for other causes.

Objective: To conduct a review of the literature available over the last 20 years regarding the use of endoprostheses at the proximal femur level for oncologic pathology.

Materials and Methods: A systematic search was conducted using the electronic databases Cochrane, Lilacs, Scielo, Pubmed, Science Direct, and the Timbó portal. The search yielded a total of 6,837 articles, of which 22 were selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria for this review.

Results: It is noted that the majority of the articles are of evidence level IV. The primary indications for their use in tumor pathology include aggressive primary tumors and metastatic disease, applicable in various scenarios such as pathological or impending fractures, salvage procedures following failed osteosynthesis or pseudarthrosis. Different options exist for repairing the abductor mechanism and capsular closure; however, the studies are heterogeneous regarding techniques, making it difficult to recommend a gold standard. Key factors to prevent instability and dislocation include the use of bipolar hemiarthroplasties and, surgically, preserving as much tissue as possible (greater trochanter, gluteus medius, fascia lata, vastus lateralis, and capsule) with the use of sutures or non-absorbable materials for repair.

The most frequent complications include dislocation (5.8%), infection (5.2%), local recurrence (4.7%), and periprosthetic fracture (0.6%). The survival rate of these prostheses ranges between 80%-90% at 5 years, while limb survival in multiple series is around 90%.

The most commonly used functional score is the MSTS.

Conclusion: We consider endoprostheses to be an excellent option within our therapeutic arsenal for proximal femur reconstruction, as they are durable, allow local treatment of the disease, relieve pain, and provide quality of life and function to patients, with a low complication rate comparable to the use of conventional prostheses for other causes.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
23 July 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

The proximal femur is a very common location for aggressive primary tumors and one of the most frequent sites in the

appendicular skeleton for the presentation of metastatic disease.

The first cases of endoprosthetic reconstruction for bone neoplasms at the proximal femur date back to 1943,

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performed by Austin Moore and Harold Bohlman. From that time until the mid-1970s, most primary sarcomas were treated with radical measures such as amputation, resulting in devastating effects on patient function and psyche.

Thanks to advances in oncology, which have achieved better local and global control of the disease, new pathways have opened for alternatives such as limb preservation and reconstruction.

This has sparked significant interest among oncologic orthopedists in achieving a reconstruction that is durable, allows local treatment of the disease without recurrence, relieves pain, and provides quality of life and function to the patient, while reducing intra- and postoperative complication rates.

There are various reconstruction alternatives, both biological and non-biological. Among the most commonly used, we highlight recycled autograft, allograft-prosthesis composites, and segmental endoprosthetic reconstruction with customized or modular implants.

The advantage of using modular endoprostheses today is that studies have consistently demonstrated that they are implants with good survival rates, high patient acceptance, reproducible functional results, and complication rates quite similar to those of conventional prostheses used for other causes, such as dislocation (5.8%), infection (5.2%), local recurrence (4.7%), periprosthetic fracture (0.6%), and limb survival (80-90%).

Due to the wide range of therapeutic options, we aimed to conduct a search on the use of modular endoprostheses at the proximal femur level, as this is an alternative available in Uruguay. Currently, prostheses from the brands Impol and LINK are available, and the procedure is funded by the FNR. In conducting this review, we sought to address the following questions:

- Most frequent indications for the use of endoprostheses in oncologic pathology (malignant or benign tumors, metastatic disease, salvage of failed osteosynthesis, pseudarthrosis).
- What is the best method to reconstruct the abductor and capsular mechanisms, including options for different clinical scenarios, and whether there is a considered gold standard.
- What are the most frequent complications reported in the published literature?
- Among functional scores, which are the most used, and which reconstructions achieve the best results?

To conclude our introduction, we would like to briefly reference three systematic reviews published on our topic by the following authors: Benjamin K. Potter, Vincent E. Chow, Sheila C. Adams, G. Douglas Letson, H. Thomas Temple, titled *Endoprosthetic proximal femur replacement: Metastatic versus primary tumors* (published in 2008); Maria A. Smolle, Dismosthenis Andreou, Per-Ulf Tunn, Andreas Leithner, titled *Advances in tumour endoprostheses: a systematic review* (published in 2019); and the most recently

published (January 2023) by Tobey D, Wing C, Calkins T, Heck RK, titled *The Use of Proximal Femur Replacement for the Management of Oncologic Lesions in the Proximal Femur: A Review*. *Orthop Clin North Am*.

General Objective

To review the current evidence on the use of proximal femur endoprostheses for oncologic pathology.

Specific Objectives

- Evaluate indications (type of primary benign/malignant tumor) (metastatic disease).
- Evaluate types of prostheses used.
- Evaluate the use of cemented vs. non-cemented techniques.
- Assess alternatives for repairing the abductor and capsular mechanisms.
- Evaluate the most frequent complications.
- Assess the functional scores used.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This work is a systematic review. The bibliographic search was conducted during the month of May of the current year. The documentary sources used were Cochrane, Lilacs, Scielo, Pubmed, ScienceDirect, and the Timbó portal. Regarding the time interval for obtaining documents, articles published from 2000 to the present were included. The keywords used were in English and included the MeSH terms: “Femur” and “Prostheses and implants”. Boolean operators included were “AND” and “OR”. Articles in free access, in Spanish, Portuguese, and English, involving patients without age criteria, and excluding animal studies, were also searched.

Inclusion Criteria

Studies were selected where the use in oncologic resection was described, in English, Portuguese, or Spanish, involving humans, without age criteria, and publications meeting the temporal search criterion (2000-2022).

Exclusion Criteria

Meta-analyses, systematic reviews, case reports, articles without initial assessment, and studies strictly evaluating the use of diaphyseal or distal femur endoprostheses were excluded. Additionally, studies mentioning animal studies, use for osteoarthritis, fractures, or infections were not included.

Search Strategy

The bibliographic selection followed the PRISMA protocol guidelines to create the flow diagram (Figure 1).

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The initial search across different platforms yielded a total of 6,837 articles. After an independent search by two reviewers, the same number of articles was confirmed. Applying the inclusion criteria resulted in 1,456 articles.

After applying the exclusion criteria, 723 studies remained. A rapid review of the titles was then conducted, reducing the number to 120 articles. Abstracts of each were read, excluding 66, leaving 54 articles for full reading. Of these, 32 were excluded, resulting in 22 articles included in this review

Figure 1. Flowchart of Article Selection

RESULTS

Table 1: Articles Included in the Review

Table 1 shows basic characteristics of the studies, including the first author, study type, publication year, documentary source, evidence level, and sample size (target population).

Tabla 1

Autor principal	Tipo de estudio	Año publicación Motor de búsqueda	Nivel de evidencia	N Muestral
D Donati	Retrospectivo	2001 / Pubmed	IV	25
Christian M Ogilvie	Retrospectivo	2004 / Pubmed	IV	29
R Wedin	Retrospectivo	2005 / Pubmed	IV	142
Yasser Farid	Retrospectivo	2006 / Pubmed	IV	72
L. R. Menendez	Retrospectivo	2006 / Pubmed	IV	96
Joseph L. Finstein	Retrospectivo	2007 / Pubmed	IV	62
C.R. Chandrasekar	Retrospectivo	2008 / Pubmed	IV	100
Hakan Selek	Retrospectivo	2008 / Pubmed	IV	44
Nicholas M Bernthal	Retrospectivo	2010 / Pubmed	IV	86
Matthew Steensma	Retrospectivo	2011 / Pubmed	III	298
M. Drexler	Retrospectivo	2015 / Pubmed	IV	65
Teresa Calabró	Retrospectivo	2016 / Pubmed	IV	109
Matthew T. Houdek	Retrospectivo	2016 / Pubmed	IV	204
GM Hobusch	Retrospectivo	2016 / Pubmed	IV	16
E.R. Henderson	Retrospectivo	2017 / Pubmed	IV	527
A Angelini	Retrospectivo	2018 / Pubmed	IV	40
J.D. Stevenson	Retrospectivo	2018 / Pubmed	IV	100
Joshua Johnson	Retrospectivo	2019 / Pubmed	IV	26
Michala Skovlund	Prospectivo	2019 / Pubmed	IV	110
Yongsung Kim	Retrospectivo	2021 / Pubmed	IV	68
John Groundland	Retrospectivo	2021 / Pubmed	IV	53
Charles A. Gusho	Retrospectivo	2021 / Pubmed	IV	38

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Table 2: Summary of Results

Table 2 presents the results of the reviewed articles, mentioning variables such as the study population (sex, age), type of primary bone tumor (benign, malignant) or metastatic disease, surgical indication, prosthesis type (cemented, non-cemented), follow-up (prosthesis survival), abductor mechanism repair, most frequent complications, and functional scores.

Autor principal	N Muestral Sexo Edad promedio	Tumor óseo	Indicación	Tipo de prótesis (Nombre prótesis subrayado)	Follow Up Supervivencia del Implante	Reparación del Mecanismo Abductor	Complicaciones	Score funcional
D Donati	N/25 19H 6/M 34 (11 a 71)	Condrosarcoma / 10 Sarcoma Ewing / 5 Osteosarcoma / 4 TCG / 2 Hemangiendoteloma / 1 Osteoblastoma / 1 Fibrosarcoma / 1 HFM / 1	Metástasis (Expectativa de vida corta)	Prótesis Modular Bipolar / Sin Cementar KMFTR	FU 12.25 Años (Media 10-16.5 años)	Anclaje a la Prótesis Glúteo Medio / (Placa Polietileno + 2 Tornillos al Trocánter Protésico)	Infección profunda / 1 Luxación / 1 Rigidez de rodilla / 1 Osteoporosis / 12 Talo Femoral (Stress Shielding) / 17	Musculoskeletal Tumor Society Satisfactorio / 17 Excelente / 7 Bueno / 10 Aceptable / 7 Pobre / 1 Reportaron dolor / 15
Christian M Oglivie	N/53 21/H 12/M 46.4 años 19 se excluyeron del análisis	Condrosarcomas / 14 Osteosarcoma / 8 Sarcomas de Ewing / 4 HFM / 2 Fibrosarcomas / 2 Osteoblastoma / 1 Teratoma metastásico / 1 Leiomiocarcinoma metastásico / 1	Tumor maligno	Endoprótesis Total de Cadera / 12 Prótesis Bipolar / 21 KMFRS / 29 WMSQS / 4	FU 3 años	Anclaje a la Prótesis / 9 Anclaje a Partes Blandas / 16 No se pudo reparar / 8 (Tumor Infiltrante)	Luxación / 3 Recurrencia tumoral / 3 Infecciones superficiales / 2 Infecciones profundas (Reemplazo en 2 tiempos) / TVP 2	MSTS 1987 Media 23 / 35 puntos. MSTS 1993 67 puntos TESC 76/100
R Wedin	N/142 69/H 73/M 69 (33 a 91)	Enfermedad metastásica / 146 Primario Mama / 32% Próstata / 25% Pulmón / 11%	Enfermedad metastásica / Fractura patológica	Endoprótesis / 109 Hemiartroplastias / 51 Bipolar / 4 PTC convencional / 45 Prótesis Tumoral / 4 Cementadas / 106 Sin cementar / 3 Hemiartroplastia Austin Moore Charnley (Depuy Synthes) Spectron (PTC)	FU 1.6 años	No menciona	Endoprótesis Cirugía de revisión / Falla (Reintervención) 9 Luxaciones / 15 (13.8%) Hemiartroplastias 2/51(4%) PTC 10/45 (22.2%) Fractura periprotésica / 4 Complicaciones sistémicas / 5.5% Locales / 4.6%	No Menciona
Yasser Farid	N/72 45/H 27/M (14-74 años)	Tumor primario / 34 malignos / 31 benignos / 3 Enfermedad metastásica / 18	Reconstrucción por tumor local	Endoprótesis / 52 Bipolar 40 Resurfacing acetabular 12 PMMA 52 Cementadas con PMMA.	FU 146 Meses Supervivencia 86% / 10 años Tumores Primarios 5/10/15 años 85%/85%/81% Enfermedad Metastásica 5 años 100%	Anclaje a la prótesis Mersilene n5. Anclaje tenodesis a la banda iliotibial / Anclaje a la prótesis Cable, Grapas, Sutura irreabsorbible Imbricación Cápsula Articular	Infecciones / 2 Alojamiento aséptico / 5 Amputación / 1 Luxación / 3	MSTS Score Endoprótesis Tumor Primario / 70% Metástasis / 68% Hip Abductor Strength Endoprótesis 2.8/5
L.R. Menendez	N/96 45/H 51/M 59 años (14-86)	Tumor maligno primario 21/22% Tumor benigno 3/0,03% Enfermedad metastásica 72/75%	No Especifica	Endoprótesis Bipolar Modular / 62 PTC / 34 Todas Cementadas con PMMA MSRS	FU 18 Meses (1-129 meses) Supervivencia 82% 5-10 años	Anclaje a partes blandas	(Fallaron) 9/ 9.3% Revisión 7/ 7.3% Amputación 1/ 1% Retiro prótesis 1/ 1% Luxación / 10,4% Infección / 6.3% Recurrencia / 3%	MSTS Score 59 pacientes Tumores óseos primarios / 21 38 Enfermedad metastásica / 38 Media 22 (15-25)
Joseph L. Finstein	N/62 32/H 30/M 49 (10-83 años)	Enfermedad metastásica / 32 Osteosarcoma / 13 Condrosarcoma / 8 Tumor de células gigantes / 5 Sarcoma Ewing / 2 Histiocitoma fibroso maligno / 1 Liposarcoma / 1	Tumor (Invasión)	Prótesis Bipolar (todas Cementadas) PFRP (Biomet) / 10 (MRSSK) / 52	FU 5 años Supervivencia a los 5 años 79%	Cables de Dall-Miles o Mersilene (Anclar el Trocánter mayor a la prótesis) / Anclaje de los tendones a la prótesis / Anclaje con sutura irreabsorbible a partes blandas	Revisión 12 / 19% Alojamiento aséptico 6 / 10% Luxación / 3 / 5% Infección profunda 3 / 5% Fractura periprotésica / 2	MSTS N/13 71%
C.R. Chandrasekar	N/100 45/H 55/M 60 años	Metástasis	Enfermedad Metastásica / Fracturas patológicas / Fijación Fallida / Riesgo de fractura	METS system	FU 15.9 Meses (0-77 meses) Supervivencia 83% 5 Años	Osteotomía del trocánter mayor (Anclaje) Placa trocantérica de anclaje / + Tornillos / + Alambre. Sutura del mecanismo abductor al Vasto lateral / Fascia lata. Sutura irreabsorbible / Agujeros trocánteróicos Reparación de la	Luxación / 3% 2/5 PTC 1/95 Hemiartroplastia. Infección / 6% Recurrencia local / 4% Desarticulación / 1%	TESS 64% (54%-82%)
Hakan Selek	N/44 23/M 21/H 55 años (29-84 años)	Enfermedad metastásica / 17 Mama / 13 Pulmón / 3 Próstata / 2 renal / 1 tiroides / 1 Gastrointestinal / 1 Leiomiocarcinoma / 1 Rabdomiosarcoma / 1 Tumor mesenquimal maligno / 1 Sin clasificar / 1 Carcinoma seno maxilar / 1	Enfermedad metastásica Fractura patológica Fractura inminente	(Prótesis Modulares) 35/77% (Resection Prosthesis System, Lima -Lto Spa, Italy; TMTS prostheses, Hipokrat Inc., Turkey) 10/22.3% Prótesis Standard o Talo largo Reemplazo Calcar (Bi-Metric / Neck Hip System, Biomet, UK) (Thompson Prostheses) Hipokrat Inc (Cementadas)	29 Fallecieron a los 2 meses (65.9%) 12 Sobrevivieron al Año (27.2%)	Reparación con puntos de Krakow a la prótesis (sutura irreabsorbible)	Infección 4%. 1/ Protrusión acetabular 2/ Alojamiento componente femoral 1/ Luxación 3/Marcha tredelenburg	MSTF Score 2 meses media 14.06. Al año 19.8

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Autor principal	N Muestral Sexo Edad promedio	Tumor óseo	Indicación	Tipo de prótesis (Nombre prótesis subrayado)	Follow Up Supervivencia del Implante	Reparación del Mecanismo Abductor	Complicaciones	Score funcional
Nicholas M Bernthal	N/86 46/M 40/H 44.5 años (10-83)	Tumores de Alto Grado 8A/IB / 43 Tumores de bajo Grado (8A/IB o Benigno) / 20 Enfermedad metastásica / 23	Tumores Alto Grado / Tumores bajo Grado / Enfermedad metastásica	<u>(Styker/Howmedica)</u> / 56 <u>(Techmedica Inc)</u> / 19 <u>(Depuy Orthopedics)</u> / 8 <u>(Austin Tx Inc)</u> / 2 <u>(Zimmer)</u> / 1 Custom Design / 32 Modulares / 54 (Cementadas)	FU 3 Meses (Media 64 meses (Rango 3-291) Supervivencia a los 5/10/20 años 93%/84%/56%	Reparación con sutura al Vasto Lateral / Vasto Medial	Revisión Componente Femoral 5/86 (5.8%) Aflojamiento Aséptico / 3 Infección / 1 Luxación / 4 Conversión A PTC 5/86 (5.8%) Amputación / 1	MSTS 53/86 Pacientes (Media 92 meses FU) Score 87% (Media 26 Rango (13-30))
Matthew Steensma	298 3 grupos Endoprótesis 197 Edad promedio 62 Clavo Intramedular 82 Edad promedio 61 ORIF 19. Edad promedio 55	Endoprótesis 47 mama / 34 pulmón / 7 Tiroides / 31 Renal / 8 Prostata / 20 Mieloma / 6 Linfoma / 7 Colocectal / 9 Urotelial / 2 Melanoma / 26 Otros	Fractura patológica Fractura incipiente Tumor maligno	Hemiartróplastias Tallo Largo cementado / 163 Hemiartróplastia Tallo Standard / 1 Reconstrucciones fémur proximal / 33 (Cementadas)	No menciona	No menciona	Falla del implante Endoprótesis 3% Grupo Endo Luxación (Ocurrió 90 Días post op). Revisión Endoprótesis 5 Luxaciones / Progresión 1 / Reemplazó total 2 3 Hemiartróplastias	No menciona
Drexler	65 37/H 28/M Edad promedio 57 (17 a 93)	Endoprótesis 65 Osteosarcoma/20 Sarcoma de Ewing/14 Condrosarcoma/9 Enfermedad metastásica/ 15 Sarcomas/4 Mieloma múltiple/3	Tumor primario / Fractura patológica	Prótesis modular bipolar HMRS / MUTARS	FU de 9 años	Reparación de la capsula a la prótesis / Sutura Vasto lateral al Glúteo / Sutura de las partes blandas anterior al VL / Isquiotibiales a nivel posterior	Cambios degenerativos acetabulares (4.6%) Brooker grado 1/2 Osiñación heterotópica 17/26% / Protrusión cabeza acetabular 9/13.8%, Revisión 12%.	MSTS Score Media de 73%
Teresa Calabró	N/109 54/ H 55/M 60 (16-88) años	Enfermedad metastásica / 70 Sarcomas / 34 Hemopatías malignas / 5	Tumor maligno primario Reconstrucción	Bipolar 93 / PTC 16 Cementadas / 55 Sin Cementar / 54 MRR	FU 2.5 años (6 meses - 9 años) Supervivencia 5/9 años 74%	Sutura del muñón Mecanismo abductor al implante y sobre la Fascia lata.	Infección 5.8% Luxación 3.9% Recurrencia local 2.9% Fractura acetabular 1%	MSTS 21 (7/30)
Matthew T. Houdek	204 112/H 92/M 59 años (11-88)	Sarcoma primario / 65 Hemopatías malignas / 26 Enfermedad metastásica / 111	Fractura patológica Extensión lesional	Endoprótesis Hemiartróplastia Bipolar 190/93% / PTC 14/7% Todas Cementadas.	FU 7 años (2-22 años) Fallecieron 166 (81%) Supervivencia 5/10 años 88%/67%	Pura String Cápsula Malla sintética (Marlex) Cápsula / Sutura Musculatura Abductora puntos de (Ethibond) (Fiberwire) A la Prótesis o Banda Iliotibial (incluyen) Fragmentos óseos del Trocánter mayor	(Revisión 22/111 Aflojamiento aséptico / 17) Infección / 16/8% Luxación / 15/7% Amputación / 3	Score Harris 73 (32-80), MSTS Score 56% (16-93%)
Hobusch	16 11/H 5/M Edad promedio 26 (11-49)	Sarcoma de Ewing / 5 Osteosarcoma / 3 Condrosarcoma / 3 Fibrosarcoma / 1 Linfoma / 1 Hemangiendoteloma / 1 Mielosarcoma / 1 Sarcoma célula claras / 1	Tumor maligno primario	Megaprótesis tumoral sin cemento Copa bipolar / Copa tripolar HMRS / GMRS / MUTARS	FU 5 años	Reparación del Mecanismo Abductor o fijación trocánterica con sutura irreabsorbible a la prótesis Fijación mecánica del trocánter utilizando ETA, LARS o los 2.	Revisión 9/16, ISOLS Failure Tipo 1/7 Tipo 2/1 Tipo 3/4 Tipo 4/3	UCLA / Modified Weighted Activity Score. Pre op Score 9/6 Post op Score 6/3 11/14 retizan actividad física. (1 o 2) deportes al día.
E.JL Henderson	527 286/H 241/M 53 años	Enfermedad Metastásica / 246 Tumor maligno primario / 236 Tumor PB maligno primario / 20 Tumor Benigno primario / 16 Desconocido / 9	No Especifica	Endoprótesis Femoral Primaria Metálica No Expandible SKMRS / SHMRS/ SMRS/ SGMRS/ (Desconocido)	No Menciona	Reparación lo más superior / Lateral Posible. Anclaje del M.Abductor a la prótesis / Uso de malla sintética Augmentación	20/4% inestabilidad	No Especifica
A Angelini	N/40, 29/M 72.5% 11/ H 27.5%. Edad Media (Dg metastásica) 63.6 años (35 a 92)	Enfermedad metastásica / mama / 20 Pulmón / 6 Mieloma/Linfoma / 6 / Riñón / 3 Prostata / 2 Tiroides / 1 Endometrial 1 / Biliar / 1	Fractura patológica Fractura incipiente	Endoprótesis convencional / 4 Endoprótesis modular / 29 Femur (Cementado/ Todas) Copa bipolar en todos los casos GMRS / MRS / MUTARS	FU 10.2 meses (6-26 años)	No menciona	Tasa de complicaciones 22.5%. 1/40 Lesión del ciliático 1/40 Luxación 3/40 Progresión tumoral 2/40 Infección 1/40 TVP	Pain intensity VAS Score MSTS Score Media 22.4
J.D. Stevenson	100 48/H 52/M 61 años (19-85)	Enfermedad metastásica / 74 Tumor primario / 20 Mieloma Múltiple / 6	Fractura patológica Fijación fallida	Unipolar 64 Bipolar 36. Custom Made 4 Prótesis Modular 96 Starrmore Implants Worldwide. Todas cementadas con ATB. 27 Collar de Hidroxiapatita.	FU 2 años (0.5 - 3.7 años) Supervivencia a los 5 años / 95%	8 Anclaje con placa 92 Sutura al Vasto lateral / Fascia Lata	No hubo luxaciones. No resurfacing acetabular 58 Muertes. Supervivencia 2 años promedio. Metástasis 1.3 años/ Tumor Primario maligno 3.16 años Revisión 3 Infección 4	ISOLS

RESULT

A total of 22 articles were analyzed, with the majority being evidence level IV (21 retrospective and 1 prospective), with variable sample sizes.

All included studies mention the use of proximal femur endoprostheses for oncologic indications, such as primary malignant and benign tumors, metastatic disease, and failed osteosynthesis.

Table 2 details each analyzed variable schematically. We first want to highlight the heterogeneity of the studies and the large number of variables involved, such as patient age range, early vs. late diagnosis, histopathological type, neoadjuvant and adjuvant systemic therapy, preoperative assessment, surgical technique, surgical indication (pathological fracture, impending fracture, PSA, tumor progression, dislocation, infection, failed osteosynthesis, periprosthetic fracture), making it challenging to unify results and draw conclusions.

Demographic Data / Surgical Indication

Regarding their use, we note that they can be applied across a wide age range as shown in the studies (14 to 90 years). The most frequent indications for endoprosthesis use include various clinical scenarios such as malignant and benign primary tumors and metastatic disease (either prophylactically or for pathological fractures). Their use is also mentioned in complex situations, such as conversion from failed osteosynthesis or pseudarthrosis.

Detailed Aspects of Each Study

The study published by **Donati et al.** in 2000 describes the use of uncemented, modular, bipolar KMFT endoprostheses in 25 patients. Among the tumors presented, malignant and benign primary tumors were highlighted, with a 10-year follow-up. The average resection length was 18.5 cm (12 to 25 cm), and the rationale for not using cement at the time was the belief that it caused greater femoral wear. The abductor mechanism was repaired by anchoring the gluteus medius to

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a polyethylene plate and screws on the prosthesis. Postoperative complications included 1 dislocation, 1 deep infection, and knee stiffness. Some cases showed complications such as loosening, acetabular wear, and aseptic necrosis of the acetabular roof. Bone resorption and osteoporosis adjacent to the implant were observed in 17 patients. Functional MSTS results were satisfactory in 17 patients.

It is noted that until 2000, the concept of bipolar reconstruction was not uniformly accepted. Its main benefits, such as reducing postoperative dislocation and maintaining good bone quality until hip resurfacing was needed, were mentioned. These authors began to question how to improve abductor mechanism reconstruction.

Christian M. Ogilvie et al. published their study in 2004, involving 29 patients with primary malignant/benign tumors with an average follow-up of 3 years. The authors posed three questions: What are the general results and complications with endoprosthesis use? Do patients achieve better function with improved abductor mechanism repair? Are functional results better with total prostheses or bipolars?

The KOTZ and WMTA prostheses were used. Abductor mechanism repair depended on tumor invasion; if it infiltrated the abductor mass, repair was often not feasible. If the tumor invaded the trochanter without soft tissue mass, it was resected en bloc, and the remnant was sutured muscle-to-muscle over the prosthesis. If oncologic resection preserved bone stock, it was anchored to the prosthesis.

Complications included dislocation in 3 patients and infections in 4. The average MSTS 93 score was 67.7, and the TESS score was 76. No significant differences were found in outcomes related to abductor mechanism repair. Functional results were similar between bipolar and total prosthesis groups.

Wedin et al. published their study in 2005, involving 142 patients with pathological fractures due to metastatic disease. Three surgical treatments were performed: osteosynthesis with a nail, DHS, and endoprosthetic reconstruction in 109 cases, with a 1.6-year follow-up. No technical details on abductor mechanism repair were provided.

The most frequent complications were periprosthetic fractures in 4 patients and dislocations in 3. The dislocation risk was five times higher with total prostheses than with hemiarthroplasties.

The authors recommend endoprostheses over reconstruction nails or other osteosynthesis implants due to lower failure rates in the proximal third of the femur and the ability to avoid complications like PSA, implant failure, or tumor progression. The reoperation rate was 8.3% for endoprostheses vs. 16.2% for osteosynthesis. No functional score was mentioned.

Yasser Farid et al. published their study in 2006, comparing 72 patients, with 52 receiving endoprostheses and 20 allograft-prosthesis composites for primary benign/malignant

tumors and metastatic disease, with an average follow-up of 146 months.

Oncologic resection was based on tumor extent, and all endoprostheses were fixed with PMMA. Abductor mechanism repair techniques included anchoring the abductor tendon to the prosthesis with Mersilene or No. 5 polyester, direct repair with prosthesis anchoring, and augmentation with iliotibial band or greater trochanter anchoring with non-absorbable sutures, cables, wires, or a trochanteric claw. Extra effort in capsular closure and abductor anchoring was recommended to reduce postoperative dislocation rates.

The most frequent complications were infection in 2 cases and aseptic loosening in 10%. The average MSTS score was 70% for the endoprosthesis group.

Lawrence Menéndez et al. published their study in 2006, including 96 patients with benign/malignant primary tumors and metastatic disease, with an 18-month follow-up. Bipolar implants were used in 34 cases and total prostheses in 62. Head size was determined intraoperatively based on soft tissues and acetabular condition. Cement was used in all prostheses, and the abductor mechanism was anchored to adjacent soft tissues without prosthesis attachment.

Implant survival was 82% at 5 and 10 years, and limb survival was 99% at 5 years. The average MSTS score was 22 points. The most significant complication was dislocation in 10 patients, requiring revision in total prosthesis cases but none in the bipolar group. Infection rates were 6.3%.

Bipolar heads are recommended to increase survival and reduce dislocation rates. Bipolar endoprostheses are considered a durable reconstruction, generally outlasting the patient, and are preferred over total hip prostheses.

Joseph Finstein et al. published their 2007 study, including 62 patients with primary malignant tumors and metastatic disease, using cemented bipolar femoral endoprostheses with an average 5-year follow-up.

Oncologic resection was based on intraoperative findings. The abductor mechanism was repaired with Dall-Miles cables to anchor the greater trochanter to the prosthesis or Mersilene tape, with non-absorbable sutures to the prosthesis or healthy soft tissues.

The most frequent complications were aseptic loosening (10%), dislocation (5%), and infection (5%). Limb survival was 98% at 5 years, and implant survival free of complications was 79% at 5 years. The average MSTS 93 score was 21.3.

Coonor Chandrasekar et al. published their 2008 study, involving 100 patients with metastatic disease, using the modular METS bipolar prosthesis with various modular heads, trochanteric anchors, femoral stems of different lengths and sizes, and hydroxyapatite collars at the bone-prosthesis interface. All were cemented.

Oncologic resection was based on intraoperative findings, with an average femoral cut of 9 cm. The abductor mechanism was repaired with a trochanteric osteotomy

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anchored to the prosthesis with a plate and screws or cables. If the greater trochanter could not be preserved, it was anchored to the vastus lateralis and fascia lata, with non-absorbable sutures to the trochanteric holes of the plate. The capsule was preserved and repaired with non-absorbable purse-string sutures around the prosthesis neck when possible. The femoral head choice depended on acetabular condition (monopolar heads or acetabular replacement).

Complications included dislocation (3%), infection (6%). Implant survival at 5 years was 83%. The average TESS score was 64%.

Radiotherapy was noted as a risk factor for infection, and dislocation was often linked to extensive soft tissue resection, including periarticular muscles and capsule. Small heads were associated with increased dislocation risk.

Hakan Selek et al. published their 2008 study with 44 patients (45 reconstructions) with metastatic disease, using modular prostheses in 35 (Resection Prosthesis System, TMTS Prosthesis, Hipokrat Inc, Turkey) and standard or long stems in 10 (Bi-metric Head/Neck Hip System, Biomet). All were cemented, with acetabular reconstruction based on its condition.

Surgery was performed in patients with a MIRELS score of 9 or higher. The abductor mechanism was repaired with Krakow stitches to the gluteus medius, anchored to prosthesis holes. The capsule was preserved and repaired with viable tissue around the prosthesis neck when possible.

The stem should extend at least two bone diameters beyond the most distal metastasis. Complications included 2 infections, 1 acetabular protrusion, 2 aseptic loosening, and 1 dislocation. The average MSTTS score was 14.06.

Given the high mortality, a minimum life expectancy of 2 months, estimated by a multidisciplinary team, was a prerequisite for surgery. Endoprostheses are recommended for proximal femur reconstruction due to benefits like local disease control and implant stability.

Nicholas Bernthal et al. published their 2010 study with 86 patients with high- and low-grade tumors and metastatic disease, with an average 3-month follow-up. They asked: What is the survival of cemented bipolar femoral endoprostheses? Are modular implants better than custom-made prostheses? Which hemiarthroplasties should be converted to total hip replacements?

Prostheses used were Stryker, Tehmedica Inc, Depuy Orthopedics, Austin TX, Zimmer, and custom designs, all cemented. The abductor mechanism was repaired with sutures to the vastus lateralis and medialis, and the capsule with non-absorbable sutures.

Complications included femoral component revision (5), aseptic loosening (3), infection (1), dislocation (4), conversion to total hip replacement (5), and amputation (1). Implant survival at 5, 10, and 20 years was 93%, 84%, and 56%, respectively. Five-year survival for metastatic disease was 16%, and for IIA/IIB disease, it was 54%, 50%, and 44%

at 5, 10, and 20 years, respectively. Limb survival was 98%. The average MSTTS score was 53.

Cemented bipolar femoral prostheses are recommended for proximal femur reconstruction, being durable and outlasting the patient, with a 5% revision rate and 99% limb survival.

Matthew Steensma et al. published their 2016 study with 298 patients with metastatic disease, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma, comparing treatments for pathological or impending proximal femur fractures: intramedullary nailing (82), endoprosthetic reconstruction (197), and open reduction with internal fixation (19). All prostheses were cemented. No details on abductor mechanism repair were provided.

Failure rates were 3.1% for endoprostheses, 6% for intramedullary nails, and 42% for osteosynthesis. Revision rates were 0.5% for endoprostheses, 6% for nails, and 42% for osteosynthesis. Complications included dislocation in 6 patients. Endoprostheses are recommended due to lower failure rates, postoperative complications, and higher implant retention.

M. Drexler et al. published their 2015 study with 65 patients with primary malignant tumors, metastatic disease, or malignant hematologic conditions, with a 9-year average follow-up. They evaluated acetabular radiographic changes after proximal femur endoprosthetic reconstruction without acetabular component replacement.

HMRS and MUTARS prostheses were used. Soft tissue repair involved capsular closure to the prosthesis head and suturing the vastus lateralis over the abductor muscles. Complications included heterotopic ossification (26%), degenerative changes (4.6%), acetabular protrusion (13.8%), and revision (8%). Of 65 patients, 44% showed radiographic changes with minimal functional impact; 64% had good or excellent results, with a 4.6% conversion rate to total hip replacement and 97% limb survival. Bipolar reconstruction is a valid option despite radiographic changes not significantly affecting function.

Teresa Calabró et al. published their 2016 study with 109 patients with primary malignant tumors, metastatic disease, or malignant hematologic conditions, with a 2.5-year average follow-up. They evaluated patient and implant survival and frequent complications.

The modular MPR prosthesis was used (93 bipolar, 16 total), with 55 cemented and 54 uncemented. Cementation was preferred for metastatic and hematologic malignancies. The abductor mechanism was repaired by suturing the stump to the prosthesis or fascia lata.

Complications included infection (5.8%), dislocation (3.9%), local recurrence (2.9%), and acetabular fracture (1%). Survival was significantly higher in sarcoma patients (58% at 5 and 9 years) compared to metastatic and hematologic patients (20% and 13% at 5 and 9 years). MPR survival was 74% at 5 and 9 years. The average MSTTS score was 21. Megaprostheses are a viable option post-proximal femur resection, with low complication rates and good implant survival.

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Matthew Houdek et al. published their 2016 study with 204 patients with primary malignant tumors and metastatic disease, with a 2-year average follow-up. Hemiarthroplasties were used in 93% of cases and total hip replacements in 7%. The capsule was repaired with a purse-string technique around the prosthesis neck; if tissue was inadequate, synthetic mesh (Marlex) augmentation was used. The abductor mechanism was repaired by anchoring the gluteus medius and vastus lateralis to the prosthesis or iliotibial band with Ethibond or FiberWire, using any remaining trochanteric fragment.

Complications included aseptic loosening (17), infection (16), dislocation (15), and amputation (3). Limb survival was 98%. Five-year survival for metastatic disease was 8%, and for primary malignant disease, 54%. Average Harris and MSTS scores were 75 and 8 postoperatively. Endoprostheses are recommended for malignant tumor reconstruction, offering durability and good postoperative function.

G.M. Hobusch et al. published their 2016 study with 16 patients with proximal femur malignant tumors, with a 5-year average follow-up. They assessed physical activity levels post-resection and megaprosthesis reconstruction.

Uncemented bipolar hemiarthroplasties (HMRS, GMRS, MUTARS) with bipolar or tripolar cups, Screw Pan, or Pedestal Cup were used. Abductor mechanism or trochanteric fixation was done with non-absorbable sutures to the prosthesis, using synthetic materials like ETA (Enhanced Tendon Attachment), LARS (Ligament Advanced Reinforcement System), or both.

Of 16 patients, 14 were active pre-surgery; at 1 year, 6/16, at 3 years, 10/16, and at 5 years, 13/16 continued regular physical activity. Scores used were UCLA and Modified Weighted Activity Score, with preoperative averages of 9 and 6, dropping to 6 and 3 postoperatively.

Complications were assessed with the ISOLS system (1-5 types: 1-soft tissue failure, 2-aseptic loosening, 3-structural failure, 4-infection, 5-local recurrence), showing 7 type 1, 1 type 2, 4 type 3, 3 type 4, and no type 5 failures.

Rehabilitation and sports have potential psychological and physical benefits for oncologic patients, but no studies show their impact on endoprosthesis survival. Limitations include a small sample and short follow-up, making definitive conclusions difficult. Nine of 16 patients required revision, but no link to sports was proven.

E.R. Henderson et al. published their 2017 study with 527 patients with primary malignant and benign tumors and metastatic disease, with no follow-up specified. They evaluated hip stability post-endoprosthetic reconstruction, assessing whether capsular repair improves stability.

No details on abductor mechanism repair or functional scores were provided. Instability occurred in 20 patients. Hip stability is influenced by patient variables, lesion type, surgical technique, and implant used. No association was found between better capsular repair and reduced instability.

A posterolateral approach, hemiarthroplasties, and synthetic augmentation for soft tissue repair confer the lowest instability risk. Female sex, elderly patients, and primary malignant/benign tumors were risk factors.

Angelini et al. published their 2018 study with 40 patients with metastatic disease, with a 10-month average follow-up. Treatments included 7 intramedullary nails, 4 conventional endoprostheses, and 29 modular endoprostheses.

Three prosthesis models were used (GMRS, MRS, MUTARS), all with cemented modular femoral stems and bipolar cups. The average resection was 160 mm. No abductor mechanism repair details were provided.

Complications included 1 dislocation, 3 tumor progressions, and 2 infections. Survival was 92% at 1 year, 83% at 2 years, and 75% at 5 years. The average MSTS score was 22.4. Endoprostheses are recommended, especially for renal carcinoma or multiple myeloma metastases.

J.D. Stevenson et al. published their 2018 study with 100 patients with primary malignant tumors, metastatic disease, or multiple myeloma, with a 2-year average follow-up.

Dislocation rates were 34%-35% with acetabular replacement for total hip prostheses. Abductor mechanism repair involved anchoring the gluteus medius with a plate to the prosthesis or to soft tissues (vastus lateralis and fascia lata).

Ninety-six modular and 4 custom-made prostheses were used, with 64 unipolar and 36 bipolar reconstructions. Twenty-seven had hydroxyapatite-coated collars for osteointegration. Large modular heads were beneficial in preventing postoperative dislocation.

Complications included infection in 4 patients and revision in 3. Survival at 2 years averaged 1.3 years for metastatic disease and 3.12 years for primary malignant tumors. No dislocations occurred. Hemiarthroplasties may eliminate short- to medium-term instability without significant acetabular wear requiring future resurfacing.

Joshua Johnson et al. published their 2019 study with 26 patients with metastatic disease, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma, with a 6-year average follow-up. They studied patients with failed osteosynthesis converted to endoprostheses.

Groups included intramedullary nails (18), DHS (5), proximal locking plate (1), angled plate (1), and cannulated screws (1). Conversion to arthroplasty averaged 13 months, with common causes being tumor progression, implant failure, and pseudarthrosis.

Bipolar and total hemiarthroplasties were used, determined by surgeon preference, acetabular condition, age, and life expectancy. No abductor mechanism repair details were provided, but good capsular closure and double-mobility implants were recommended to reduce dislocation rates.

Five-year survival was 25%. Complications included infection in 4, instability in 2, and disease progression in 1. Antibiotic-impregnated cement is recommended to reduce infection rates, especially in irradiated bone or prior failed osteosynthesis. The Harris score improved from 24

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preoperatively to 68 postoperatively, and MSTs from 14 to 59. Endoprostheses improve quality of life and allow immediate weight-bearing as a salvage procedure.

Michala Skovlund et al. published their 2019 study with 110 patients, all with metastatic disease, with a 2-year follow-up. Forty-four received osteosynthesis implants, and 66 received endoprostheses (bipolar/total hemiarthroplasties).

No abductor mechanism repair details were provided. The score improved from 12 to 23 points 6 months post-surgery. Complications included dislocation in 6 patients. The 2-year implant failure risk was 7% for osteosynthesis vs. 2% for endoprostheses. The revision risk was 7% for osteosynthesis vs. 5% for endoprostheses. Endoprostheses are recommended due to low implant failure risk, short hospital stays, and good MSTs scores.

Youngsung Kim et al. published their 2021 study with 68 patients with primary malignant tumors and metastatic disease, with a 55-month average follow-up.

All cases used MUTARS bipolar hemiarthroplasties, with some uncemented and cement used if the femoral cut was very distal. Resection was determined intraoperatively based on the tumor.

The abductor mechanism was repaired by anchoring the gluteus medius and vastus lateralis to a mesh or wrapped in a Trevira tube over the prosthesis, with trochanteric osteotomy and cable anchoring to the prosthesis.

Complications included infection (4%), local recurrence (9%), acetabular erosion (4%), and implant loosening (3%). Implant survival was 83.9% at 5 years and 59.8% at 10 years. Two-stage revision is the most effective treatment for prosthetic infection, and silver-coated implants remain debated for infection reduction. Modular bipolar endoprostheses are recommended due to low complication rates and good local disease control.

John Groundland et al. published their 2021 study with 53 patients with primary malignant tumors, malignant hematologic conditions, and metastatic disease, comparing abductor mechanism repairs: one group with trochanteric osteotomy and another with soft tissue anchoring to the prosthesis. Follow-up was every 3 months for 2 years, then every 6 months up to 3-5 years.

Repair method depended on tumor type and surgeon preference, favoring trochanteric osteotomy when possible. Forty-eight cases used bipolar hemiarthroplasties and 5 total prostheses. Trochanteric dissociation from the endoprosthesis was radiographically evident in 45% of cases. Only 10% of the osteotomy group and 38% of the soft tissue group resumed normal life without a Trendelenburg gait.

No statistically significant differences were found between repair methods; trochanteric osteotomy did not improve functional outcomes, Trendelenburg gait, or device use like canes.

Charles A. Gusho et al. published their 2021 study with 38 patients with primary malignant bone tumors and metastatic disease, evaluating endoprosthesis survival post-oncologic

resection, with a 23-month average follow-up. Mostly bipolar hemiarthroplasties were used.

They referenced Henderson's failure classification (1-soft tissue, 2-aseptic loosening, 3-structural failure, 4-infection, 5-tumor progression). No abductor or capsular repair details were provided.

Limb survival was 97%, consistent with literature due to good local disease control. Complications included a 14.6% revision rate at 5 years and 7% dislocation rate. Endoprostheses are recommended as a durable option outlasting the patient.

DISCUSSION

We reviewed the current literature on proximal femur endoprostheses in oncologic pathology, which presented methodological complexity due to the heterogeneity of the reviewed articles and the approach and therapy provided by each author and center.

Resection and prosthetic replacement of the proximal femur remain the treatment of choice for malignant tumor pathology. The era of oncologic reconstruction has undoubtedly changed the functional prognosis and, more importantly, the psychological pillar for patients, given the significant consequences of limb amputation.

Endoprostheses are a good therapeutic option due to their advantages: adaptability to various clinical scenarios thanks to modularity and design, good patient acceptance, excellent pain relief, good function, suitability for skeletally mature and immature patients, complication rates similar to conventional prostheses for other causes, and preference as the implant of choice for failed osteosynthesis or pseudarthrosis in oncologic pathology.

Regarding different clinical scenarios, their versatility and applicability stand out: pathological fracture, tumor progression, pseudarthrosis, failed osteosynthesis, and use even in patients with short life expectancy when performed by trained hands.

Complications reported in the reviewed articles are broad, including dislocation, superficial and deep infection (early and late), local tumor recurrence, disease progression, bone resorption of components, periprosthetic fracture, Trendelenburg gait, postoperative inguinal pain, amputation, and death.

The ISOLS score is the most used, dividing failures into 5 types. No gold standard exists for abductor and capsular mechanism repair due to variable clinical scenarios. Preserving more healthy tissue and anchoring it to the prosthesis and healthy tissue is considered a repair with a good prognosis, reducing dislocation, infection, postoperative pain, and limp risks. Many authors recommend non-absorbable sutures or augmentation techniques.

Failure rates across most variables are similar to conventional prostheses for fractures and osteoarthritis. Functional scores used include MSTs, Hip Abductor Strength, TESS, Harris Score, UCLA, Modified Activity Score, Pain Intensity VAS

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Score, and Trendelenburg test, with MSTs being the most common.

Studies suggest a mechanical and functional advantage with bipolar hemiarthroplasties, being more stable and yielding better functional scores, reducing postoperative dislocation rates. Bipolar endoprostheses preserve the acetabulum with minimal bone changes, allowing future conversion to total hip replacement if needed. Studies report limb salvage rates of around 80% with this therapy.

LIMITATIONS

We note that this review includes articles with low scientific evidence (level IV), mostly case series, with different populations, tumor types (benign, aggressive, metastatic), surgical indications (failed osteosynthesis, pathological fracture, tumor progression), systemic therapies (chemotherapy, radiotherapy, hormone therapy), and surgeons (varying expertise), making reliable result obtention difficult. Nonetheless, we believe it provides a good approximation to real-world outcomes.

CONCLUSION

We consider it appropriate to adapt the surgical technique to the clinical scenario and the infrastructure and materials available to the surgeon, recognizing that the most controllable factor, regardless of the prosthesis, is planning and surgical technique. Greater care in musculoskeletal tissue dissection allows for more anatomical reconstructions and thus better functional outcomes.

We consider endoprostheses a valuable tool in our therapeutic arsenal, enabling durable reconstruction, relatively easy access, local disease and pain treatment, and improved quality of life and function for patients.

The systematization and approach to patients with oncologic pathology should be conducted by a multidisciplinary team, from diagnosis to treatment. Optimizing the patient's systemic status and preoperative and postoperative planning are critical before proximal femur prosthetic replacement.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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